

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18456513>

IDEOLOGICAL ASPECTS OF THE SOVIET GOVERNMENT'S STATE POLICY TOWARDS WOMEN

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ABSTRACT

This article comprehensively analyzes the structure, tasks, areas of activity of women's organizations in Uzbekistan during the Soviet era, and their impact on society. The article examines the role of organizations in social transformation in relation to the traditional values of the Uzbek people. During the Soviet era, women's organizations were important social institutions established to actively involve women in political, economic, and cultural life. Their main goal was to ensure women's education, increase their literacy rate, ensure their employment, and encourage them to actively participate in building a new society within the framework of Soviet ideology. These organizations tried to reconcile the traditional family role of women with the new social requirements of the Soviet era and performed many social tasks in the creation of the "new Soviet woman." In general, although women's organizations promoted Soviet ideology, they played an important role in improving the social activity and legal status of women in society. That is, although the essence and purpose of these organizations were based on Soviet ideology, they served to ensure social progress and equality between men and women.

Index Terms: Soviet era, Uzbekistan, women's organizations, social transformation, Uzbek people, traditional values, society, political, economic and cultural life, social institutions, education, literacy rate, employment, Soviet ideology, rights and opportunities, problems, political and social activism, religious and national traditions, conflicts, central policy, Soviet ideology.

INTRODUCTION

As is known, in the early years of Soviet power, the "Women's Question" was resolved based on the interests of the state, which was implementing a program of economic modernization of the country. The 1920s were characterized by an increased attention of the Soviet authorities, the leaders of the Communist Party and the heads of

state to instilling in the public consciousness the image of a "new" person, including a "new" woman. The image of the "new" woman had specific "Soviet" features, that is, a socially active woman, a hardworking woman who often visited libraries, reading rooms, and literacy schools, was contrasted with the traditional pre-revolutionary image of a woman who was an "illiterate and uncultured" housewife, tormented by the "religious superstition" of the recent past.

The sources state that the directions and tasks of the women's sections are as follows: "Their first task is to educate female workers and peasants in the spirit of communism and attract them to our party. The second task is to attract the mass of women to Soviet construction... The third task of the sections is to put forward to the party issues such as taking into account the specific characteristics of women by gender (for example, laws on motherhood, protection of women's labor, abortion) in the process of building Soviet society. Because the Soviet policy on the issue of women's attitude required the alienation of women from the family. Therefore, at the first meeting of the organizers of the Eastern Women's Party, held on April 5-7, 1921, issues such as the development of a "Decree on Freedom of Divorce" and a "Decree on Marriage Age and Marriage"[25] were on the agenda. In June 1921, the Central Executive Committee of the Soviets of the Turkestan ASSR A decree was adopted prohibiting the marriage of underage girls and polygamy, and abolishing dowry. The marriageable age was set at 16 years instead of the 9 years prescribed by Sharia law[26]. Chapter 10 of the Criminal Code of the RSFSR was "On the fight against the vices of old age in the family and household life", and dowry was defined as buying a bride[27]. Also, the III session of the Supreme Soviet of the Uzbek SSR in 1928 adopted a new law on marriage for the Uzbek SSR. According to it, the age of marriage for teenage boys was set at 18, and for girls at 16. At the same time, marriage had to be concluded on the basis of the consent of both parties. The law prohibited a couple from entering into a second marriage without a legal separation from the first marriage. It was established that both spouses have equal rights in the matter of divorce[28]. This is a positive aspect of the law. "Dowry and Weeks and even days were set for the fight against "polygamy" and events were held. One of the resolutions they issued also included a clause that said: "Divorce cases should be considered no later than one week." [29] Because during the "Attack" period, the courts received a huge number of divorce applications, which were from women who were dissatisfied with forced marriages and wanted to separate from their elderly husbands, relying on the new Soviet laws mentioned above, such as the prohibition of polygamy, marriage without the consent of girls, and the abolition of the "Kal" (the "old man's wife"), and who wanted to separate from their elderly husbands. As a result, the policy pursued by the Soviet authorities in matters of family and marriage led to the breakdown of thousands

of families, the wandering of children between their parents, the spread of "Kaydi-Chikidi" (a type of "spouse-wife"), the devaluation of the family and the loss of its social status, and the punishment of women who filed applications by their husbands, fathers, or brothers. [30] Because, for centuries The traditional way of life during the 19th century ensured a privileged position for men in the family. The revolutionary changes in the family and marriage issues of the Bolsheviks, which came with great force, dealt a severe moral blow to men, but they also pushed women towards an unimaginable "bright life". This led to the deprivation of women from their true happiness, the family. Also, as a result of the fact that women's activities within the family were condemned and not valued as a type of social work, the family was separated from its social status and turned into household chores.

Ensuring legal equality of women with men, their broad involvement in public affairs, their participation in the management of society and the state, and the collectivization of households in the conditions of the socialist revolution were the main tasks set by the authorities in solving the "women's question". For this purpose, women's departments and delegates' meetings were used to mobilize women for labor and political work, to turn them into social activists. Despite the government's efforts to free women from "domestic slavery", the traditional concepts of women as mothers, wives, and housewives were not erased from everyday life.

Although the activities of women's organizations in Uzbekistan during the Soviet period were essentially organized on the basis of Soviet ideology, they have significant scientific and historical significance in the context of modern gender policy. During the Soviet era, women's organizations, established under the leadership of the Communist Party, were important social institutions aimed at ensuring the active participation of women in social, political and economic life and played an important role in the construction of a socialist society. The activities of these organizations were associated with conflicts associated with local cultural and religious traditions. Their goal was to promote women's education, employment and equal rights in Soviet society on the basis of Soviet ideology. The Soviet government effectively used the activities of women's departments in implementing its autocracy policy. The Soviet government relied on revolutionary changes in the issue of the role of women in the socio-economic and cultural life of society, relying on measures based on administrative-command policies. These organizations played an active role in the process of harmonizing women's traditional family values with the requirements of Soviet ideology. However, due to political restrictions, religious and cultural contradictions, and territorial conditions, their activities were complex and contradictory, in accordance with the goals and interests of the communist ideology. The study of the activities and problems of women's organizations in the Soviet period

is relevant for a deeper understanding of gender equality and the status of women in society. It is also important from a scientific point of view to study the colonial nature of the Soviet attitude towards women by comparing it with the attention paid to women in our country today.

METHODS AND LEVEL OF STUDY

The article uses historical, comparative analysis, periodic problematics, the principles of objectivity, and a comprehensive approach to study the role, goals, and objectives of women's organizations in the Soviet period. In addition, in order to clarify the essence of the topic raised in the article, the results achieved in the activities of women's organizations and their contradictory nature are analyzed using the works of R.Kh. Aminova "October and the solution of the women's question in Uzbekistan", D.A. Alimova "Women's question in Central Asia. History of study and modern problems", Ya.A. Abdullayeva "Women of Karakalpakstan: yesterday and today (late 19th century and 20th century)", R. Madrakhimova "Labor and military feats of women of Uzbekistan during the Great Patriotic War", G.N. Kameneva "Activity of women's councils in solving social problems: history and modernity", N.W. Popova "On the role of women in a socialist society".

RESULTS OF THE STUDY

During the Soviet period, women's organizations served as an important tool for social, economic and political activities carried out in the interests of communist ideology. These organizations, in particular, Although the Women's Committee and local Women's Councils (zhenotdel) were promoted as being established to ensure women's equality through open policies, increase their participation in education and labor, and protect their rights, in fact, the main goal was to shape the interests of Soviet policy. In republics such as the Uzbek SSR, these organizations operated in conflict with local traditions and national culture.

During the Soviet period, women's organizations in Uzbekistan played an important role in changing the position of women in social, economic, and political life. Established under the leadership of the Communist Party, these organizations performed important tasks in implementing Soviet policies aimed at strengthening women's rights and ensuring equality in education and labor.

After the October Revolution of 1917, ensuring equality between men and women was declared one of the main directions of state policy. In December 1918 By special instruction of the Central Committee of the RCP(b), a proposal was put forward to establish local commissions for propaganda and agitation among women. August 1919 After the idea of establishing special bodies to work with women was approved by the party council, the commissions were transformed into women's departments within the party committees.

Representatives of the Soviet government, proceeding from the goals and interests of their colonial and nationalist policies, in order to achieve socio-political activity of women of the local ethnic group, on November 12, 1919, the Women's Department of the Turkestan Regional Committee of the RCP(b) was established[2]. The main task of the Women's Department was to involve women workers and peasants in party and state work, to increase their political consciousness and worldview, and to increase their socio-political activity. In carrying out this task, the main activity of the Women's Department was aimed at conducting systematic propaganda work, organizing rallies, lectures, rally-concerts and theatrical performances among women. Brochures for women were published. The editorial staff of the newspaper "Ishtirokiyun" published popular brochures in Uzbek for local women on political topics such as "Sizga so'zim", "Onalarga", etc. [3]. A special page for women workers was opened in the regional newspaper "Izvestia".

In December 1919, a women's department was established in the Tashkent city party committee under the leadership of L. Dvorkina [4]. Among its members were activists of the women's movement Z. Yusupova, F. Redkina, M. Khusanbayeva, Z. Karimova, Z. Burnasheva, M. Gafarova, Lisovaya and others who constantly carried out propaganda work among women in factories and factories[5]. After that, special attention began to be paid to the issue of organizing women's departments in the regions. In particular, instructor L.I. Shumileva was sent to Fergana and Syrdarya to organize similar departments[6]. As a result, women's departments began to be organized in all regions under the responsibility of leading women of European and Tatar origin who came from the center[7].

The women's movement department under the Turkestan regional committee of the RCP(b) was reorganized as a regional department for work with women with a staff of 5[1]. This department systematically operated in accordance with two other departments, namely, those carrying out organizational and propaganda work. In 1920, the women's department of the Turkestan regional committee managed 45 local women's departments (jenotdel), uniting 9 thousand women, while by 1921 the number of local women's departments had reached 61, of which 7 were established in the regions, 31 in the uyezds and 23 in the districts. The number of active women in these departments amounted to 16 thousand people[8]. In particular, in Kokand, T. Shodiyeva, T. Ibragimova, K. Karimberdiyeva, T. Mavlyanbekova (March 1919), in Andijan, Kh. Abdurahmanova, G. Abdullayeva, R. Ismailova, R. Ismatullayeva (November 1919), in Samarkand, F. Niyazova, T. Juraboyeva, M. Kobilova, in Fergana, O. Kholmatova, Khadichakhon (last name not preserved in documents) (February 1920), in Syrdarya, Sh. Goyibjonova, in Bukhara, G. Abdullayeva (November 1920), and M. Khusanbayeva in the Kashkadarya region are among these

active and leading women[9]. In Karakalpakstan, in February 1920, a working women's union was formed in Petro-Aleksandrovsk (Turtkul), initially consisting of 30 people, and at the end of that year it was transformed into a women's department of the city party committee. This department began to operate in practice in 1925. Its organizers were mainly women of Russian nationality[10]. It is worth noting that in order to educate local women politically and socially, leading women of Russian and Tatar nationality were attracted from the center[11]. The main task of their activities was to strengthen work among local women. Since the "problem of emancipation" of women occupied a special place in the socio-political life of the 1920s, ideological and production factors of influence on women's activities were organized.

The activities of the women's departments were organized in the following three main areas:

1. Strengthening political education and activism: To widely involve women in the processes of "socialist construction" through propaganda and agitation activities and to implement various forms of activities aimed at raising their political consciousness (various forms of socio-political meetings (rallies, rallies, congresses, congresses, conferences, meetings, councils), cultural events, incentives). Using the women themselves in these activities, to form a socially active, "leading" and "benevolent" layer of women of the communist party, to promote the "communist lifestyle".

2. Ensuring economic independence: Increasing the socio-economic activity of women through socio-practical activities related to competitions, specially organized brigades and links, "social tugs", working days, weekly, monthly, contests, and social gatherings aimed at ensuring their economic independence and artificially accelerating labor productivity by involving women in relevant artels and trade unions.

3. Organizing cultural and educational institutions: Raising the educational and cultural level of women through the organization of schools for the elimination of illiteracy, specially organized training and advanced training courses, clubs and various circles, propaganda points, and other cultural and educational institutions.

The Soviet government's policy towards women in these areas, although aligned with the interests of communist ideology, was an important factor in increasing the activity of Eastern women in the socio-political, economic and cultural spheres and strengthening their position in society. However, the underlying goal of the measures taken was to use women's labor as much as possible and "productively", and these measures served to educate a completely new generation of women who wanted to actively participate in society on an equal footing with men, rather than in the family. Women's organizations also played an important role in strengthening women's rights. The Soviet government adopted laws protecting women's rights in matters of marriage,

divorce and inheritance. In particular, decrees "On Equal Pay for Women and Men for Equal Work" and "On the Protection of Motherhood and Childhood" were adopted[12], kindergartens were established, and benefits were provided to women with many children. The first Soviet Constitution of 1918 granted women the right to vote and be elected to public office along with men.[13] However, archival documents show that the social conditions for the implementation of the tasks set out in the adopted normative documents were not created. In particular, although the policy of "liberating" women was a legal issue, it was not paid attention to the fact that this was a matter of religious and traditional society, not social and economic norms. Ambiguities in laws and decrees caused difficulties in their practical implementation.

Women's organizations were responsible for implementing these laws at the local level and explaining their rights to women. Women's organizations promoted laws to protect women's rights, for example, combating early marriage and polygamy. In Uzbekistan, the "Attack" campaign was an important part of this process, although it faced local resistance. The organizations actively promoted women's suffrage and raised their political consciousness. However, because women's organizations operated under the strict control of the Communist Party, their activities were often focused on serving Soviet ideology. This led to a neglect of the real needs of local women. For example, although the organizations encouraged women to work in industry and agriculture, the working conditions were often harsh and dangerous. In addition, the activities of women's organizations in Uzbekistan clashed with local traditional values. Radical reforms of the Soviet authorities, such as the opposition to religious traditions, provoked discontent among the local population. Women's organizations tried to reconcile this conflict with local customs, but these efforts were not always successful. Uzbek society was based on a patriarchal system, and women's active participation in public life was not accepted in many families. For example, sending girls to school or encouraging women to work was met with resistance from parents. The "Take Off the Burqa" campaign is a prime example of this resistance. Many Uzbek women were reluctant to give up their traditional clothing because it would compromise their personal and cultural identity. In some cases, this resistance turned violent, as in the 1920s, when

In the Rgana Valley, attacks were reported on activists of women's departments. The organizations worked with local leaders to resolve the problem, but the process was slow and complicated. The "Throwing Off the Burqa" campaign (1927) was promoted as a symbol of women's liberation. Women's organizations encouraged women to participate in this campaign, which helped women to become more openly involved in public life. Although this campaign was met with resistance, it encouraged women to think about their rights.

Starting in March 1920, branches for working with women were established under the Women's Department[14]. In 1921, the Women's Department of the Turkestan Regional Committee of the RCP(b) was transformed into the Women's Department of the Turkestan KP MQ[15].

In the first half of the 1920s, the central principle of Soviet policy towards women was to grant them full rights. This goal was used to modernize the country's economy, based on the interests of the state, which needed women's labor. In order to widely involve women in production and public work, they had to be "liberated" from the family. Thus, granting women equal rights with men was, first of all, against the stereotypes established in society of women running the household, raising children, and staying at home. By 1930, the "women's question" was considered to have been resolved, and as a result of the dissolution of the women's departments by the decision of the Central Committee of the All-Union Communist Party (Bolsheviks) of January 5[16], the publication of the magazines *Kommunistka* in 1930 and *Yangi Yo'l* in 1934 was discontinued. The resolution stated that the functions of the women's sections were transferred to the party committee and its departments, and were transformed into a special sector[17]. The sectors were tasked with scientifically and practically reinforcing the conclusion of the Soviet government and the Communist Party that the "women's question had been resolved." Responsibility for the overall measures taken among women was transferred to the Commissions for the Improvement of Labor and Life[18]. The commissions had more than 100 members throughout the republic, which was far from being able to carry out the large-scale work assigned to the commissions. Therefore, in May 1930, the commissions were transformed into committees operating within the republican, regional, city and local executive committees of the Union, and in 1932, they were liquidated as bodies that had completed their tasks[19]. In fact, the reason for this process was the Soviet authorities and the Communist Party's attempt to involve women in social production under the slogan of "economic liberation", to use their labor as cheap labor and turn them into the main productive force of society, and to achieve their goal, as well as the growing social and political activity of women, who were fighting for their rights and growing dissatisfaction with the policies pursued by the authoritarian regime against them.

In general, the Soviet authorities and the Communist Party, using all forms and methods of the administrative-command system, sought to attract women of local ethnic groups to the social and political front, recruit them into the party ranks, and gain their supporters in building a "new socialist society". As a result, the social and political consciousness and activity of Uzbek women increased to a certain extent. An attempt was made to artificially spread the patriotic and nationalistic feelings inherent in the nature of Uzbek women to the territory called the Union, and the policy aimed

at not forming their political and legal consciousness did not allow the awakening of the innate needs necessary for the realization of national identity and the struggle for independence.

Since during the war years it became necessary to increase the social activity of women, to increase their role as a decisive social force in the national economy, the women's departments were reorganized for a short time in May 1943 by the decision of the Central Committee of the All-Union Communist Party (Bolsheviks), and the direction, forms and methods of their work were significantly developed and complicated. In particular, in accordance with the resolution of the Central Committee of the All-Union Communist Party of the Soviet of theThe following tasks were assigned to the women's departments:

- to strengthen party-political and mass-educational work among women;
- to organize the work of women aimed at comprehensively strengthening the front and rear;
- to assist in organizing the necessary assistance to the families of fighters. These departments carried out propaganda work among women through trade unions and other public organizations in order to increase their socio-political activity. Although these organizations were legally independent, in fact they implemented the party's policy based on its instructions[20].

In the post-war years, the goals and objectives of the women's department were implemented, as before, without separating them from the goals and objectives of the entire Soviet society. In the late 1950s and early 1960s, women's councils began to be formed in enterprises, institutions, collective farms and state farms to organize and lead work among women. Because in 1956, the Soviet Women's Committee was established. In a number of places, district and city women's councils were established. Women's councils were especially actively formed in the Soviet republics of Central Asia. In Uzbekistan alone, in 1964, there were 5,760 women's councils, uniting 93,000 leading and active women. This figure was 240,000 throughout the Union[21]. Their leaders made a worthy contribution to ensuring the active participation of "Soviet women" in the development of the national economy, science, technology and culture[22]. However, in the late 1960s and 1970s, the activities of women's councils began to decline. Only in the second half of the 1980s, firstly, due to the "perestroika" policy of the center, and secondly, in connection with the 60th anniversary of the "Attack" movement, did the activities of women's councils begin to revive again. At the All-Union Conference of Women held in January 1987, a number of decisions were made aimed at improving the situation of women. In particular, these included improving women's working conditions, ensuring labor protection, paying attention to hygiene and health issues in enterprises and organizations, satisfying their cultural and

household needs, involving them in mass sports, and paying attention to preschool educational institutions and children's sanatoriums[23].

In Soviet times, women's organizations, as social institutions, were intended to protect women's rights in society and align them with the goals of the working class. This system, organized within the framework of communist ideology, had its impact on local traditions and specific social systems. That is, the role of women in society was radically changed. Through women's organizations, women were given the opportunity to receive education, employment, and be active in society. However, it is known that these organizations operated under the control of the communist party and served ideological goals.

In general, the colonial essence of communist ideology in the approach of the Soviet authorities to the issue of women's treatment was manifested in the following:

The Soviet regime forcibly imposed its laws and ideology on local societies. Through women's organizations, control was established over local women, their traditional values and relationships were trampled. Within the framework of the repressions of the Soviet political order, the goal was not to free women, but to subordinate them to the new system. Through this, cultural leadership and social control were seized in local regions. Although Soviet-era women's organizations were initially aimed at protecting women's rights and ensuring social equality, they can also be viewed as a tool of colonialism for communist ideology. These organizations exerted pressure on local culture and served to change the traditional programs and lifestyles of women, and as a result, they became one of the mechanisms of social control of the Soviet colonial system.

In conclusion, it is worth noting that the Soviets used women in socio-political life to achieve the ulterior goals of their colonial policy. In particular:

- the Soviets sought to attract local ethnic women to the socio-political front, recruit them into the party ranks, and gain their supporters in building a "new socialist society";
- they tried to artificially spread the patriotic and nationalistic feelings inherent in Uzbek women to the territory called the Union;
- the Soviets pursued a policy aimed at using local women for selfish purposes and not forming their political and legal consciousness;
- this, in turn, awakened the innate needs of local representatives to understand their national identity and fight for independence He didn't let it go.

REFERENCES:

1. Dmitrieva S.A. "Khujum means offensive." - Tashkent: Uzbekistan, 1987. - Page 21.

2. Aminova R.Kh. October and the solution to the women's issue. - Tashkent: Fan, 1975. - Page 52.
3. There.
4. Aminova R.Kh. October and the solution of the women's question. – Tashkent: Fan, 1975. – P.52; For five years. Collection on the work of the Communist Party among the women of Central Asia. – Moscow, 1925. – P.118-119.
5. There.
6. Over the past five years. A collection of papers on the work of the Communist Party among the women of Central Asia. Moscow, 1925, p. 112
7. Aminova R.Kh. October and the Resolution of the Women's Question. Tashkent: Fan, 1975, p. 63
8. Aminova R.Kh. October and the Resolution of the Women's Question. Tashkent: Fan, 1975, p. 64
9. Dmitrieva S.A. Khujum means an offensive. Tashkent: Uzbekistan, 1987, pp. 38-40.
10. Abdullaeva Ya.A. The history of the struggle of the Communist Party for the emancipation of women in Karakalpakstan...–T.: - B.88; Hujum means offensive. – P.91; Bikkulova Z.M. From the history of the struggle of the Communist Party for the emancipation of women in Karakalpakstan.// Social sciences of Uzbekistan.1962. No. 1. – P.29.
11. UzNA. R-17- fund, list 1, file 286, sheet 126.
12. Constitution (Basic Law) of the Turkestan Republic. T.: Publishing House of the Commissariat for National Dalam. 1918; Collection of decrees and orders of the Council of People's Commissars of the Turkestan Federative Republic. T.: 1918. – P. 33; The Great October Revolution and the emancipation of women in Central Asia and Kazakhstan (1917-1936). Collection of documents and materials. 1971. – P. 46-47.; Resolutions and resolutions of the congresses of the Communist Party of Turkestan 1918-1934. T.: State Publishing House of the Uzbek SSR. 1958. – P. 193.)
13. There.
14. Aminova R.Kh. October and the solution to the women's issue in Uzbekistan. – T.: Fan. 1975. – P.71.
15. Abdullaeva Ya.A. Women of Karakalpakstan... – P.69.
16. Alimova D.A. Women's issue in Central Asia... – Tashkent: Fan, 1991. – P. 62.; Abdullaeva Ya.A. Women of Karakalpakstan... –P.69.
17. Alimova D.A. The women's question in Central Asia... - T.: Fan. P. 63; Riesel F. Achievements and shortcomings in work among women // Party building. 1935. No. 4. – P. 19-24; Galperstein Ya. Women and cadres // National economy of Central Asia. 1930. No. 9-10. – P. 36.).

18. Madrakhimova R. Labor and military valor of Uzbek women during the Great Patriotic War. – Tashkent: Fan, 1981. – P.14.
19. Juraeva N. Attitude towards women in Uzbekistan (on the example of the 20-80s of the 20th century): a textbook. – Tashkent: Publishing House of the National Library of Uzbekistan named after Alisher Navoi, 2013. – 146 p.
20. Каменева Г.Н. Деятельность женсоветов в решение социальных вопросов: история и современность. 2014// [file:///C:/Users/User/Downloads/ deyatelnost-zhensovetov-v-reshenii-sotsialnyh-voprosov-istoriya-i-sovremennost. pdf](file:///C:/Users/User/Downloads/deyatelnost-zhensovetov-v-reshenii-sotsialnyh-voprosov-istoriya-i-sovremennost.pdf)
21. Попова Н. В., О роли женщин в социалистическом обществе. – Москва, 1967. – 96с.; <https://search.worldcat.org/de/title/659471796>; Равноправие женщин в СССР. Материалы международного женского семинара. – Москва, 15 сент. – 1 окт. 1956, М., 1957.,-32с.
22. Каменева Г.Н. Деятельность женсоветов в решение социальных вопросов: история и современность. 2014//[file:///C:/Users/User/Downloads/ deyatelnost-zhensovetov-v-reshenii-sotsialnyh-voprosov-istoriya-i-sovremennost.pdf](file:///C:/Users/User/Downloads/deyatelnost-zhensovetov-v-reshenii-sotsialnyh-voprosov-istoriya-i-sovremennost.pdf)
23. UzNA. R-34- fund, list 1, file 266, sheet 601.
24. UzNA. R-17- fund, list 1, file 286, sheet 126.
25. Inoyatov T.T. "The Courts of Soviet Uzbekistan in the Fight Against Relics." Tashkent, Proceedings of the Central Asian State University, 1958, issue 124, book 4, page 18.
26. "The Shariat of Central Asia: A Guide to the Development of Sharia Laws." Yangi yul. 1929, no. 4, page 8
27. "The National Economy of Central Asia." 1930, no. 9-10, page 35.
28. New history of Uzbekistan. Uzbekistan during the period of Soviet colonialism. Second book. –Tashkent, 2000. –P. 376.